

NATURAL RESOURCE GOVERNANCE AND THE RIGHTS OF RESOURCE-BEARING COMMUNITIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract :

Resource governance refers to the systems, processes, and frameworks through which authority and accountability over natural resources are exercised. It also encompasses the participation and inclusion of various groups, such as men, women, indigenous peoples, and resource-bearing communities in the management and equitable distribution of the benefits derived from these resources. At its core, the concept is anchored on the principle that governments and decision-makers, as trustees and custodians of natural resources, must manage them in a socially just and environmentally sustainable manner. This calls for inclusive governance and fair benefit-sharing within the extractive energy ecosystem to promote the well-being of both humans and biodiversity. This paper explores the extent to which resource-bearing communities in Nigeria are involved in the governance of natural resources extracted from their territories. Using a doctrinal research methodology, the paper finds that, historically, these communities have had very minimal say over decisions concerning resource management. Instead, they have borne the brunt of environmental degradation and health crises linked to extractive industry activities. These grievances have given rise to conflicts, including militancy and kidnappings, particularly in affected areas, signaling an urgent need to revisit Nigeria's approach to resource governance. In response, the Nigerian federal government has introduced some legal frameworks aimed at involving host communities in the petroleum and mining sectors. This paper critically assesses these emerging frameworks and evaluates their potential to address the long-standing concerns and expectations of resource-bearing communities.

Keywords: *Conflicts, Host Communities, Governance, Natural Resources, Sustainability, Rights*

1. Introduction

The principle of 'trust' in resource governance recognises the collective ownership of natural resources. It obliges leaders, as custodians and trustees, to manage these resources in a manner that is both socially just and environmentally responsible.¹ This approach is critical, as poor resource governance can foster a sense of marginalisation among resource-bearing communities, often resulting in unrest and conflicts. In many advanced democracies², the right to sustainable, equitable, and fair management and distribution of resource-

¹ Yemi Oke, Right-Based Approach to Energy and Natural Resources Governance in Nigeria, (2013) 2 *The Nigerian Journal of Public Law*, University of Lagos, pp. 53-78

² For example, USA, Canada and South Africa

derived benefits is acknowledged as a legally enforceable entitlement. There is a growing global consensus in support of granting clear and enforceable resource rights to these communities as a means of mitigating tensions surrounding resource control.³

In Nigeria, the framework for natural resource governance is vaguely articulated within certain provisions of Chapter II of the 1999 Constitution (as amended). Unfortunately, these provisions are legally unenforceable because socio-economic rights under this chapter are non-justiciable by virtue of Section 6(6)(c) of the Constitution.⁴ This constitutional limitation, stemming from the non-enforceability of Chapter II of the Constitution, which outlines the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy, has long been a source of contention, contributing to ongoing tensions between resource-bearing communities, the government, and extractive industry operators. The persistent exclusion of host communities from decision-making processes and benefit-sharing arrangements from resource extraction, despite bearing the brunt of environmental and socio-economic consequences, has adversely affected the nation's stability and economic performance, underscoring the urgent need for a rethink. While the government maintains that it recognises the special stake of host communities due to their proximity to resource sites and their exposure to associated negative impacts, it is nevertheless quick to invoke section 44 of the Constitution, which vests the ownership and control of mineral resources in the State.⁵ Consequently, it argues that these resources are national assets, not belonging to any individual or community, and must therefore be managed in the interest of all Nigerians. The Petroleum Industry Act, 2021 also codifies these principles by providing that “the property and ownership of petroleum within Nigeria and its territorial waters, continental shelf and exclusive economic zone is vested in the Government of the Federation of Nigeria”.⁶

Resource governance is not only crucial in curbing restiveness and militancy in resource-bearing communities, but it is also good for sustainable development, which has been defined as “*the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs*”.⁷ The ultimate focus of both governance and sustainable development is to achieve economic growth, social progress, and environmental protection for current and future populations. The importance of the concept of resource governance in Nigeria, and indeed across Africa, cannot be overstated. It holds the promise of fostering long-term sustainability while mitigating conflicts arising from the exploitation of natural resources.

2. What are Natural Resources?

Since the subject of this paper is *natural resources*, it is perhaps apt to start by defining them. Thus, natural resources are “raw materials extracted directly from the ground or soil. They are found naturally embedded in the soil and can only be modified by man for his benefit and use”.⁸ In the words of Aladeitan, they are “*a gift*

³ Yemi Oke, (n.1)

⁴ See generally Chapter II of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as Amended)

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ See Section 1 of the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021

⁷ See the Brundtland Report of the UN World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987.

<<https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/139811?v=pdf>> accessed 28 June 2025

⁸ T. Okonkwo, Ownership and Control of Natural Resources under the Nigerian Constitution 1999 and Its Implications for Environmental Law and Practice. *International Law Research*; Vol. 6, No. 1; 2017 <doi:10.5539/ilr.v6n1p162> accessed 28 June 2025

of nature and an endowment of comfort that makes the existence of mankind complete."⁹ Natural resources exist on the planet, independent of the activities and actions of humans.¹⁰ Natural resources are generally divided into two broad categories: renewable and non-renewable. The focus of this paper, however, is on non-renewable energy resources, which encompass fossil fuels such as coal, oil, and natural gas, along with valuable minerals like gold, copper, iron, and diamonds. When managed responsibly, these resources have the potential to significantly boost national prosperity by driving economic growth and development. However, history bears witness to the fact that, if mismanaged, they can also become triggers for violent conflicts, agitations, and unrest, highlighting the critical importance of fair and responsible stewardship in managing them.

3. What is 'Governance'?

The definition of 'governance' is largely dependent on the context of its usage. For this paper, governance can be defined as "systems and processes by which decisions are made and implemented within a society or organisation."¹¹ It involves the deployment of political power and institutional resources to address issues and manage public affairs in society.¹² The World Bank in 1992, defined governance as *'the way power is exercised in managing a country's economic and social resources for development'*.¹³ Expanding on this, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) describes governance as *'the exercise of economic, political, and administrative authority to manage a nation's affairs across all levels; and this includes the mechanisms, institutions, and processes that allow citizens and groups to express their interests, uphold their rights, fulfill responsibilities, and resolve conflicts'*.¹⁴

The UNDP's definition above places significant emphasis on the political and social aspects of governance, a focus clearly reflected in its nine criteria of 'Good Governance'¹⁵, namely:

- (1) *Participation*: Every individual, regardless of gender, should have a voice in decision-making, either directly or through legitimate intermediate institutions that represent their interests. Such broad participation is built on freedom of association and speech, as well as the ability to engage meaningfully in civic processes.¹⁶
- (2) *Rule of law*: Justice must be dispensed in a fair and unbiased manner, particularly in the enforcement of laws on human rights.¹⁷

⁹ L. Aladeitan, 'Ownership and Control of Oil, Gas, and Mineral Resources in Nigeria: Between Legality and Legitimacy' (2013) *Thurgood Marshall Law Review*, Vol. 38:159 at 160.

¹⁰ Natural Resources – Definition, Types and Examples, *Geeks for Geeks*, April 8, 2025 <<https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/social-science/natural-resources-definition-types-and-examples/>> accessed 28 June 2025

¹¹ A. Biswas, 6 Types of Governance Explained: Meaning and Dimensions. *School of Political Science* (2025). <<https://schoolofpoliticalscience.com/definitions-and-types-of-governance/>> accessed 29 June 2025

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ World Bank (1992): *Governance and Development*. Washington DC.

¹⁴ United Nations Development Programme (1997): *Governance for sustainable human development: A UNDP Policy Document*. United Nations Development Programme.

¹⁵ See Environmental Information Service, *Namibia/EIS*. <<https://the-eis.com/>> accessed 29 June 2025; See also UNDP (n.14)

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

(3) *Transparency*: Openness and unrestricted access to information are the bedrock of transparency. Sufficient information must be available for people to question, understand, evaluate, and monitor the systems, processes, and institutions.

(4) *Responsiveness*: Institutions and systems should respond promptly and effectively to the needs of all stakeholders, ensuring inclusive service delivery.

(5) *Consensus orientation*: Good governance should encourage consensus building among diverse interests to reach agreements that serve the larger public good and shape fair policies and procedures.¹⁸

(6) *Equity*: Everyone, regardless of background or gender, should have equal opportunities to enhance or maintain their quality of life without any let or hindrance.¹⁹

(7) *Effectiveness and efficiency*: Governance systems should deliver on their goals while optimising the use of available resources for maximum impact.²⁰

(8) *Accountability*: Those in decision-making roles, whether in government, the private sector, or civil society, must be accountable to the public and relevant stakeholders for their actions.

(9) *Strategic vision*: Leaders and citizens should have a broad and long-term perspective on good governance, focusing on sustainable development and long-term goals that promote human well-being.²¹

Although originally designed with nation states in mind, these nine principles of good governance are broadly applicable across various levels and types of administration (including natural resource governance), since the nine criteria are universally formulated and characterise policy processes in general.²² As a result, the concept of good governance has already been widely adopted very frequently in research and practice, and it has been used, among other things, to examine how natural resources, public goods, and protected areas are managed.²³

4. Natural Resource Governance

Natural resource governance encompasses the frameworks, systems, and practices that shape how authority and responsibility over natural resources are allocated and exercised, and how citizens - men, women, indigenous peoples, and local communities - participate in and benefit from the administration of natural

¹⁸ Cooper, A. (2007). *Governing Global Health: Challenge, Response, Innovation* (J. Kirton, Ed.) (1st ed.). Routledge.

<<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315585550>> accessed 29 June 2025

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

²⁰ Environmental Information Service, Namibia (n.15)

²¹ *Ibid.*

²² C. Weidner (2019) *The Importance of Good Governance for Community-Based Natural Resource Management: Evidence from Conservancies in the Zambezi Region, Namibia. A Study written for the Ministry of Environment and Tourism's NAMPARKS IV Project, implemented by GOPA.* <<http://the-eis.com/elibrary/sites/default/files/downloads/literature/>> accessed 28 June 2025; See also Environmental Information Service, Namibia (n.15)

²² *Ibid.*

²³ P.F. Eagles, F. Romagosa, W.C. Buteau-Duitschaever, M. Havitz, T.D. Glover, and B. Mccutcheon (2012): Good Governance in protected areas: an evaluation of stakeholders' perceptions in British Columbia and Ontario Provincial Parks. *In: Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 21(1): 60-79.

resources.²⁴ Put in another way, it is the management and oversight of natural resources such as coal, oil, natural gas, water, as well as valuable minerals like gold, copper, iron, and diamonds.²⁵ It includes the systems, frameworks, policies, and institutions that govern how these resources are explored, extracted, utilised, and distributed. At its core, natural resource governance involves those rules and procedures that define who controls the allocation of rights to, and the use of, natural resources. Crucially, the way power is distributed and exercised plays a central role in shaping both the governance process and its outcomes.²⁶ Resource governance has also been defined as a ‘*set of strategies aimed at promoting transparency and accountability in how natural resources are managed*’.²⁷

The ‘governance’ element is therefore concerned with who holds authority and responsibility, and how these are exercised to influence access to, and benefits from, natural resources.²⁸ Strengthening natural resource governance by securing rights and sharing decision-making power leads to positive outcomes for both the resource-bearing communities and biodiversity. Ultimately, good governance forms the backbone of a fair and sustainable world, one that protects nature and supports the realisation of global sustainable development goals.²⁹

5. Multiple Level Resource Governance

There are different levels of resource governance systems. However, the focus here is on those that fall within the purview of multiple levels of governance.³⁰ Multi-level governance emphasises the interaction of numerous actors operating across different administrative levels and geographical scales.³¹ It is within this context that the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) developed the *Natural Resource Governance Framework (NRGF)*.³² This initiative provides a comprehensive, inclusive, and credible method for evaluating and improving natural resource governance across a range of diverse settings. The core objective of the NRGF is to establish standards and provide guidance that empower decision-makers at all levels to make fairer, more informed choices about how natural resources are used and how the benefits of nature are shared. By upholding

²⁴ J. Campese, (2016). *Natural Resource Governance Framework Assessment Guide: Learning for Improved Natural Resource Governance, IUCN/CEESP NRGF Working Paper*. IUCN and CEESP, Gland.

²⁵ For the purpose of this paper, reference to natural resource governance shall be limited to the management of oil, gas and mineral resources only.

²⁶ G. Barnes, Introduction, in G Barnes, B Child (eds.), *Adaptive Cross-Scalar Governance of Natural Resources* (London: Routledge, 2014), pp. 3– 10.

²⁷ Acosta, A. (2010). Review of impact and effectiveness of transparency and accountability initiatives, Paper prepared for the Transparency and Accountability Initiative Workshop October 14 –15, Institute of Development Studies, Sussex

²⁸ F. Nunan, *Navigating Multi-level Natural Resource Governance: An Analytical Guide*, 2018 - Natural Resources Forum. <<https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-8947.12149>> accessed 29 June 2025

²⁹ See Natural Resource Governance Framework|IUCN <<https://www.iucn.org/commissions/commission-environmental-economic-and-social-policy/our-work/knowledge-baskets/natural-resource-governance>> accessed 29 June 2025

³⁰ F. Nunan (n. 28)

³¹ G Armitage, Governance and the commons in a multi-level world. *International Journal of the Commons*, 2008, 2(1): 7– 32. See also E Mwangi, A Wardell, Multi-level governance of forest resources. *International Journal of the Commons*, 2012. 6(2): 79– 103.

³² Springer, Jenny, Campese, Jessica, Nakangu, Barbara, *Natural Resource Governance Framework/IUCN*; International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), Year 2021 <<https://www.iucn.org/commissions/commission-environmental-economic-and-social-policy/ourwork/knowledge-baskets/natural-resource-governance>> accessed 28 June 2025

principles of good governance, the aim is to strengthen governance systems in ways that boost the role of ecosystems and biodiversity in promoting equity and long-term sustainability.³³

6. Key elements of Natural Resource Governance:

- a. *Transparency and Accountability*: One of the key elements of natural resource governance is transparency and accountability. These elements ensure that natural resources are managed in a manner that is transparent, accountable, and devoid of corruption. Transparency in this context means that decision-making processes are open and understandable, the rationale behind decisions is clearly communicated, and relevant information about governance and industry performance is readily accessible to all. In essence, it involves making critical information about the handling of the natural resource sector and related investments available to stakeholders and local communities.³⁴ For Nigeria, this would encompass the availability of accurate and verifiable data on general technical information concerning actual production, revenue receipts, and utilization. Also, it relates to social and environmental responsibility information concerning how the State and its commercial partners manage and respond to local stakeholders' issues, including the environment. Accountability, on the other hand, involves assigning and accepting responsibility for decisions and actions, along with demonstrating how these responsibilities have been fulfilled. In the extractive industries, accountability also entails adherence to regulatory requirements. This includes the degree to which governments and other stakeholders comply with relevant laws, codes, and standards, and maintain a compliance framework in line with their operational and financial strategies. It also involves having systems in place to monitor compliance, such as internal and external audits, as well as processes for fulfilling external reporting obligations.³⁵
- b. *Sustainable Development*: Central to natural resource governance is the goal of promoting sustainable development through the effective management of natural resources balancing economic, social, and environmental considerations. The concept of sustainable development first emerged in public and academic discourse in 1972 with the publication of the Founex Report, and gained renewed attention in 1987 with the release of the Brundtland Report, formally titled *Our Common Future* by the World Commission on Environment and Development. This report offered a widely accepted definition of sustainable development as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs."³⁶ Another interpretation of sustainable development describes it as the practice of preserving productivity by replacing used resources with alternatives of equal or greater value, without harming or threatening natural ecosystems.³⁷ Over time, the concept has evolved to emphasise a balance between economic growth, social well-being, and environmental protection for the

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ A.I. Osawe and G. O. Uwa (2023) Natural Resource Governance and Conflicts in Nigeria, *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Advanced Studies: Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences* 4(1):17-35; <DOI:10.37745/bjmas.2022.0103> accessed 28 June 2025

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ See Brundtland Report – A publication by World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987.

<<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Brundtland-Report>> accessed 26 June 2025

³⁷ Lynn R. Kahle, Eda Gurel-Atay, eds (2014) *Communicating Sustainability for the Green Economy*. New York: ME Sharpe. ISBN 978-0-7656-3680-5.

benefit of future generations. This aligns with the Brundtland Report, which underscored three key pillars of sustainable development —environment, society, and the economy —and offered several important recommendations for advancing sustainability.

The United Nations (UN) General Assembly took further steps toward sustainable development by integrating its three core dimensions—economic development, social development, and environmental protection —as interdependent and mutually reinforcing pillars. In this spirit, the UN established the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which aim to tackle a wide range of global challenges, including poverty, inequality, climate change, environmental degradation, peace, and justice. The SDGs comprise 17 interconnected global objectives that serve as a "blueprint for achieving a better and more sustainable future for all."³⁸ They were adopted in 2015 by the UN General Assembly, with a target for full implementation by 2030. Over time, the concept of sustainable development has expanded beyond its original focus on intergenerational equity to emphasise "socially inclusive and environmentally sustainable economic growth."³⁹ There is a clear nexus between natural resource governance and sustainability, which can be understood as a hierarchy of goals and constraints encompassing global, regional, and local considerations.⁴⁰

- c. *Stakeholder Engagement*: This has become a core component of resource governance.⁴¹ Stakeholder engagement entails inclusive and participatory processes that bring together local communities, civil society organisations, the private sector, and other relevant parties in decision-making. In the context of natural resource management, stakeholder engagement means involving these groups in planning and decision-making to incorporate their knowledge, values, and perspectives into specific projects or initiatives.⁴²

This process is crucial for addressing potential conflicts of interest, integrating diverse viewpoints, and enhancing accountability while reducing uncertainties.⁴³ Thus, involving stakeholders in a systemic way and engaging them through inclusive, reflective, and adaptive processes is essential for the effective management of natural resources.⁴⁴ It is, however, important to identify who is to be engaged in the stakeholder engagement process. Numerous principles, frameworks, and methodologies have been

³⁸ United Nations (2017) Resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 6 July 2017, Work of the Statistical Commission pertaining to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (A/RES/71/313)

³⁹ Sachs, Jeffrey D. (2015). *The Age of Sustainable Development*. New York: Columbia University Press. ISBN 9780231173155.

⁴⁰ Sathaye, J., Lucon, O., Christensen, J., Rahman, A., Denton, F., Fujino, J., Heath, G., Kadner, S., Mirza, M., Rudnick, H., Schlaepfer, A., Shmakin, A., & Masanet, E. (2011). Renewable Energy in the Context of Sustainable Energy. In O. Edenhofer, R. P. Madruga, & Y. Sokona (Eds.), *IPCC Special Report on Renewable Energy Sources and Climate Change Mitigation* (pp. 707-790). Cambridge University Press. <[https:// www.scholars.northwestern.edu/en/publications/renewable-energy-in-the-context-of-sustainable-energy](https://www.scholars.northwestern.edu/en/publications/renewable-energy-in-the-context-of-sustainable-energy)> accessed 27 June 2025

⁴¹ Z. Han, Y. Wei, F. Bouckaert, K. Johnston, and B. Head, Stakeholder engagement in natural resources management: Where go from here? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 435, 5 January 2024, 140521 <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.140521>> accessed 28 June 2025

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ Ibid,

⁴⁴ Ostrom, E., 2010. Polycentric systems for coping with collective action and global environmental change. *Global Environ. Change* 20, 550–557. <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2010.07>> accessed 27 June 2025

developed to guide the identification of stakeholders and the design of participatory processes that address complex issues, such as resource scarcity and environmental pollution.⁴⁵

One widely recognised framework outlines five key features of effective stakeholder engagement, namely: (i) defining clear objectives, (ii) identifying relevant stakeholders, (iii) selecting appropriate engagement methods, (iv) fostering shared ownership of decisions, and (v) providing feedback on outcomes. These steps serve as practical guidelines for planning, implementing, and evaluating stakeholder engagement efforts. Ultimately, systematically involving stakeholders through inclusive, adaptive, and reflective approaches is vital for the successful and sustainable management of natural resources.⁴⁶

- d. *Revenue Management*: Managing the revenue generated from natural resources in a way that benefits both the country and its citizens is another vital component of resource governance. Revenue management here refers to how a government administers, allocates, distributes, and oversees income from natural resources, whether through national budgets, natural resource funds, state-owned enterprises, subnational governments, or direct cash transfers to citizens.⁴⁷ Governments face unique challenges in handling resource revenues due to their volatility, finite nature, and potential to trigger the “resource curse.” This phenomenon can harm other sectors of the economy, foster corruption and rent-seeking behaviour, and even lead to conflict. As such, resource revenues often require distinct management strategies compared to other public funds.

Effective management of resource revenue is crucial for resource-dependent countries like Nigeria, as these nations are usually vulnerable to two key monetary risks: excessive foreign capital inflows that lead to currency overvaluation, and general macroeconomic instability. This instability characterised by fluctuating prices, exchange rates, and GDP, can result in what is known as the “Dutch disease.”⁴⁸ One way to mitigate this is through monetary sterilization, where the central bank offsets capital inflows by purchasing foreign currency or selling domestic bonds. Indeed, most oil-rich nations actively manage their exchange rates through their central banks.⁴⁹ For any revenue management system to succeed, strong oversight mechanisms are essential. Oversight ensures transparency in how revenues are received and distributed, establishes clear rules for revenue allocation, and enforces regular audits and reporting. It also includes legal safeguards to prevent and punish corruption and misuse of funds.⁵⁰

⁴⁵Mitchell, R.K., Agle, B.R., Wood, D.J., 1997. Toward a theory of stakeholder identification and salience: defining the principle of who and what really counts. *Acad. Manag. Rev.* 22 (4); see also Prell, C., Hubacek, K., Reed, M., 2009. Stakeholder analysis and social network analysis in natural resource management. *Soc. Nat. Resour.* 22 (6), 501–518. <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-019-00749-x>> accessed 28 June 2025

⁴⁶ Talley, J.L., Schneider, J., Lindquist, E., 2016. A simplified approach to stakeholder engagement in natural resource management: *The Five-Feature Framework*. *Ecol. Soc.* 21 (4) <<https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-08830-210438>> accessed 28 June, 2025

⁴⁷ See NRG Reader, *Revenue Management and Distribution: Addressing the Special Challenges of Resource Revenues to Generate Lasting Benefits*. A publication of Natural Resource Governance Institute, March 2015 <https://resourcegovernance.org/sites/default/files/nrgi_Revenue-Management.pdf> accessed 29 June, 2025

⁴⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁹ Ibid, 7

⁵⁰ Ibid.

7. Host Communities' Participation in Natural Resource Governance

a. *The Tragedy of the Commons*

The *tragedy of the commons* is a well-known concept in resource governance, popularised by ecologist *Garrett Hardin* in his 1968 essay titled "*The Tragedy of the Commons*."⁵¹ The theory suggests that when individuals have unrestricted access to shared public resources, they tend to act in their own self-interest, seeking to maximise personal gain without considering the broader impact on society. For example, a shepherd might continue adding more cattle to a shared grazing field to increase his own production, disregarding the cumulative damage this might cause the land.⁵² Although each individual benefits in the short term, the cost of overuse is spread among all users. Eventually, this leads to overexploitation and the degradation of the resource beyond its capacity to regenerate.⁵³ *Hardin* argues that this type of unchecked self-interest could lead to the inevitable collapse of the resource system.⁵⁴ He emphasised the need for societies and nations to facilitate the preponderation of public good and interest over individual or sectional aspirations to avoid what he considers the ruinous tendency of unregulated freedom.⁵⁵ To avoid this outcome, *Hardin* concluded that as population and demand grow beyond a resource's carrying capacity, individual freedoms and access to common goods must be regulated.⁵⁶ Understanding this theory is essential to implementing sustainable management of public goods like natural resources. It highlights the role of governments in preventing the tragedy of the commons through transparent, equitable governance of shared resources, especially by addressing the concerns of communities most directly affected by resource exploitation.

b. *Governing the Commons*

Given the natural tendency of man to be self-centered and look after his interests, as highlighted by the theory of 'tragedy of the commons' above, scholars have explored real-world examples of shared resource use, like forests, fisheries, grazing lands, and irrigation systems, to identify what drives sustainable management.⁵⁷ Leading this work, Elinor Ostrom presented her findings in *Governing the Commons* (1990),⁵⁸ outlining eight principles for successful communal resource governance, including clearly defined boundaries, adaptable rules, community-led decision-making, monitoring, graduated sanctions, and mechanisms for conflict resolution, rights to self-organise, and multi-level institutional structures.⁵⁹ Although these principles have

⁵¹ G. Hardin (1968) *The Tragedy of the Commons*. In: *Science* 162: 1243-1248; See also Environmental Information Service, Namibia (n.15)

⁵² C. Weidner (2019) *The Importance of Good Governance for Community-Based Natural Resource Management: Evidence from Conservancies in the Zambezi Region, Namibia. A Study written for the Ministry of Environment and Tourism's NAMPARKS IV Project, implemented by GOPA*. <<http://the-eis.com/elibrary/>> accessed 27 June 2025; See also Environmental Information Service, Namibia (n.15)

⁵³ Ibid.

⁵⁴ G. Hardin (n.51) and also Environmental Information Service, Namibia (n.15)

⁵⁵ Ibid. See also C. Weidner (n.52)

⁵⁶ Ibid.

⁵⁷ C. Weidner (n.52), See also Environmental Information Service, Namibia (n.15)

⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁵⁹ Ibid.

been reviewed and criticised, including by Ostrom herself, the overall consensus remains consistent.⁶⁰ Critics have challenged the idea that her *framework* applies universally, highlighting other key success factors. Notably, social dynamics such as trust, transparency, and legitimacy often play a more decisive role than variables like group size, boundary clarity, or homogeneity. For example, social factors often help explain why resource management succeeds in certain communities but falls short in others.⁶¹ Success is, therefore, not solely dictated by factors such as population size, homogeneity, or well-defined boundaries; but rather, social dynamics, including trust, transparency, and legitimacy within the community, play a critical role in shaping effective resource management and governance.⁶²

c. The Context for Community Rights in Resource Development

The basis for community rights in resource development is anchored on two important foundations – (i) ‘*interest in or connected to resource development area*’ and (ii) ‘*adverse impacts*’. On the first foundation, i.e., ‘*interest in, or connection to resource development area*’, a community is considered a ‘host’ if upstream or midstream exploration, production, or transportation activities occur within territory where the community has legal or historical ties.⁶³ Resource extraction activities often affect and even impede the host community’s ownership or usufruct rights, limiting or even halting their lawful, traditional uses of the ecosystem. Consequently, these communities are entitled not only to compensation but also to participation in significant decisions involving mineral operations. The second foundation, i.e., ‘*impacts*’, focuses on the unique adverse social and environmental harms experienced by host communities due to their proximity to resource extraction sites. Beyond the legal constraints on their rights, these communities often suffer environmental degradation, such as severe pollution that destroys or diminishes essential life-sustaining resources of the ecosystem on which rural community survival depends, thereby undermining rural livelihoods.⁶⁴ The consequences include increased poverty, reduced ability to meet basic needs, health issues, and lower life expectancy, frequently falling below national rural averages. Despite these burdens on resource-bearing host communities, basic amenities and services from the various tiers of government are often lacking, fueling resentments, agitations, and conflict directed at both the government and mineral rights holders.

It is in the acknowledgement of these factors that many jurisdictions across the globe are increasingly recognising host community rights in resource development by introducing different hard or soft law mechanisms that outline the nature and extent of these rights. In Nigeria, the Federal Government acknowledges the rights of host communities in the main statutes that regulate the petroleum and mining sectors. The Nigeria Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) 2021, for instance, contains provisions on host

⁶⁰ Ibid.

⁶¹ M. Cox, G. Arnold & S. V. Tomas (2010): A review of design principles for community-based natural resource management. *In: Ecology and Society*, 15(4): 38.

⁶² I. H. Harkes (2006) Fisheries co-management, the role of local institutions and decentralisation in Southeast Asia: with specific reference to marine sasi in Central Maluku, Indonesia. Doctoral Thesis, *Leiden University*. ISBN (print) 9789090206974.

⁶³ National Assembly, Petroleum Industry Act. See section 318 which defines a host community as a community situated in or appurtenant to the area of operation of a settlor, including any other community as a settlor may designate.

⁶⁴ Ako, R. (2013). *Environmental Justice in Developing Countries* (1st ed.). Taylor and Francis. Retrieved from <<https://www.perlego.com/book/1675307/environmental-justice-in-developing-countries-perspectives-from-africa-and-asiapacific-pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025

communities' rights and mandates the establishment of a host community development trust fund, a structured framework that entitles impacted communities to benefit from extractive activities in their domain⁶⁵

i. A Summary of Community Rights under the Petroleum Industry Act (PIA)

Chapter 3 of the PIA establishes the framework for the compulsory institutionalisation of the Host Community Development Trust Fund (HCDTF) throughout the petroleum industry. Section 234 outlines the four important objectives of the Trust.⁶⁶ They are to (i) foster sustainable prosperity in communities, (ii) provide direct industry-induced social and economic benefits, (iii) eliminate conflicts between communities and the industry proponents, and (iv) create a framework for community development.⁶⁷ This framework is still at the early stages of implementation. However, if constructively implemented, it will enhance community participation towards their development and sustainability.

ii. A Summary of Community Rights under the Minerals and Mining Act, 2007

The Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act, 2007,⁶⁸ can be regarded as a trailblazer in formally recognising community rights in Nigeria's mining sector. It was the first national legislation to create community expectations and legal entitlements for resource-bearing host communities in minerals development.⁶⁹ The Act officially took effect on March 29, 2007, replacing the earlier Minerals and Mining Act No. 34 of 1999. To ensure the full implementation of its provisions, the Ministry of Mines and Steel Development introduced the Minerals and Mining Regulations in 2011. Under Section 116 (1) of the Act, every holder of a Mining Lease, Small-Scale Mining Lease, or Quarry Lease *must*, before beginning any development, enter into a Community Development Agreement (CDA) with the host community. The main objective of this agreement framework is to facilitate the transfer of economic and social benefits resulting from the mining industry to host communities. Until recently, the application and enforcement of provisions of the Mining Act remained largely untested in the sector. This was essentially due to the largely artisanal nature of the Nigerian mining industry.

However, the Honorable Minister for Solid Minerals Development, Mr. Dele Alake, and his Ministry are trying to embed this statutory requirement within the sector. In 2024, the Ministry announced the

⁶⁵ I. Ozu and E. Cyril-Hart, Incorporation of host communities' development trust under Petroleum Industry Act. *The Guardian Newspaper*, 17 January, 2023 <<https://guardian.ng/features/incorporation-of-host-communities-development-trust-under-petroleum-industry-act/>> accessed 27 June 2025

⁶⁶ O.J. Jegede and W. Idiaru, Host Community Development Funds in Nigeria – Establishment and Procedure, Mondaq, September 21, 2021 <<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/leasing/1113096/host-community-development-funds-in-nigeria-establishment-and-procedure/>> accessed 28 June 2025

⁶⁷ Ibid.

⁶⁸ National Assembly, Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act 2007 <<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/nig92382.pdf>> accessed 28 June 2025

⁶⁹ V. Dania, Community Development Agreement Provisions in the Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act, 2007; and the Nigerian Minerals and Mining Regulations, 2011 - *African Centre for Leadership, Strategy & Development (Centre LSD)*, March 9, 2022 <<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/community-development-agreement-provisions-?>> accessed 28 June 2025

release of Guidelines for the production of CDAs.⁷⁰ The Guidelines outline key components that must be integrated into a Community Development Agreement (CDA), namely - stakeholder participation, monitoring frameworks, infrastructure commitments, environmental protection, compensation clauses, dispute-resolution procedures, and a review cycle every five years.⁷¹ This initiative has already yielded tangible results. By the end of 2023, approximately 252 mining companies had entered into CDAs with their respective host communities.⁷²

These initiatives are a major step forward in recognising host communities' right to participate in the benefits of resource exploitation in their communities. Despite these advancements, strict enforcement remains vital as ensuring its ultimate success will depend on consistent implementation, government oversight, and effective compliance mechanisms. Commendably, the federal government has made it clear that, going forward, any company that fails to sign a compliant Community Development Agreement (CDA), risks losing its mining licenses.⁷³

iii. Limitation of the Petroleum and Mining Frameworks

While these two sectoral frameworks give host communities the right to participate more actively in social and economic development, including potentially charting the pathway for community sustainability through setting and pursuing long-term socio-economic agendas for themselves, they do not grant any community the right to determine who is granted mineral rights within their communities. The latter falls squarely within the exclusive rights to ownership, control, and management of minerals constitutionally allocated to the federal government by Section 44(3) of the Constitution. Under Section 44(3) of the Nigerian Constitution, all minerals, including petroleum and natural gas, within Nigeria's land, territorial waters, and Exclusive Economic Zone remain the property of the Federation, managed exclusively by the federal government.⁷⁴

d. Community-Based Natural Resource Management

In response to the *tragedy of the commons*, the Community-Based Natural Resource Management (CBNRM) framework was introduced in the 1990s. CBNRM seeks to promote inclusive resource governance, where local communities and resource users actively participate in decision-making, with management, enforcement, and

⁷⁰ Banwo & Ighodalo, 'Highlights of the guidelines for the production of Community Development Agreements in the Solid Mineral Sector' - Published in Business Day: September 19, 2024 <<https://businessday.ng/news/legal-business/article/highlights-of-the-guidelines-for-the-production-of-community-development-agreements-in-the-solid-mineral-sector/>> accessed 28 June 2025

⁷¹ Ibid.

⁷² Sami Tunji, "Dele Alake says 252 mining companies agree to provide basic infrastructures to host communities" – in Nairametrics, November 16, 2023 <<https://nairametrics.com/2023/11/16/dele-alake-says-252-mining-companies-agree-to-provide-basic-infrastructures-to-host-communities-in-nigeria/>> accessed 29 June 2025

⁷³ M. Izuaka, Community Guidelines: Nigerian government to revoke mining licences. *Premium Times*, January 30, 2025 <<https://www.premiumtimesng.com/business/663685-community-guidelines-nigerian-govt-to-revoke-mining-licences.html?tztc=1>> accessed 29 June 2025

⁷⁴ See s. 44(3) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as Amended)

regulatory roles integrating local institutions, customary practices, and traditional knowledge.⁷⁵ Early applications of the CBNRM framework yielded impressive results, such as the recovery of wildlife populations that had been devastated by poaching, habitat loss, and the tragedy of the commons.⁷⁶ At its core, the CBNRM model advocates that natural resources are best managed by local, collective institutions that prioritise the widespread benefits for the community. It entails devolving decision-making authority and rights over local resources to communities and community-based organisations, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of resource management through genuine community participation.⁷⁷ Devolution, in this context, involves creating relatively autonomous layers of authority, responsibility, and rights, where primary accountability lies with the communities they are meant to serve.⁷⁸ Initiatives such as Zimbabwe's CAMPFIRE program and Namibia's communal wildlife conservancies highlight the transformative impact of devolving authority over wildlife resources and eco-tourism to local communities.⁷⁹ By granting these communities control, they have been able to generate substantial revenue and enhance wildlife conservation efforts. In this context, *devolution* signifies the establishment of fairly autonomous zones of governance and responsibility, where local entities are chiefly accountable to their own populations. In the context of Community-Based Natural Resource Management (CBNRM), *devolution* refers to the process of shifting authority over natural resources to independent, decentralised bodies or administrative units that are primarily answerable to the local communities within their jurisdictions.⁸⁰ Without genuine devolution and deliberate adaptation to local power structures and circumstances, CBNRM risks falling short of its stated goals of equitable and sustainable resource governance.

8. Criticisms of CBNRM

The CBNRM model has been criticised for falling short of the high expectations associated with its implementation and the devolution of natural resource rights.⁸¹ The first criticism is that real devolution does not occur, as formal steps are rarely followed, and central authorities retain legal control over resources.⁸² Additionally, benefit distribution is frequently inequitable. Restrictions on resource use to protect the

⁷⁵ D. Armitage (2005) Adaptive capacity and Community-based Natural Resource Management. In: *Environmental Management*, 35(6): 703-715; See also Community-based natural resource management (cbnrm) IPBES Secretariat <<https://www.ipbes.net/ar/node/40894?utm>> accessed 28 June 2025

⁷⁶ C. Weidner (n. 45); See also Environmental Information Service, Namibia (n.15)

⁷⁷ See Factsheet: CBNRM Overview/Resource Africa <<https://www.resourceafrica.net/factsheet-cbnrm-overview/>> accessed 28 June 2025; See also D. Armitage (n. 75)

⁷⁸ M.W. Murphree (2000) Boundaries and borders: the question of scale in the theory and practice of common property management. In: *Eighth Biennial Conference of the International Association for the Study of Common Property*, 31.

⁷⁹ See CBNRM Impact – *Sustainability Directory*, 04.04.25 <<https://sustainability-directory.com/term/cbnrm-impact/>> accessed 28 June 2025; See also C. Weidner (n. 52)

⁸⁰ C. Weidner (n. 45); See also Environmental Information Service, Namibia (n.15)

⁸¹ C. M. Shackleton, T. J. Willis, K. Brown, N.V.C Polunin. Reflecting on the next generation of models for community-based natural resources management. *Environmental Conservation*. 2010; 37(1):1-4 <<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/environmental-conservation/article/reflecting-on-the-next-generation-of-models-for-communitybased-natural-resources-management/>> accessed 28 June 2025; See also Environmental Information Service, Namibia (n.15)

⁸² Environmental Information Service, Namibia (n.15)

environment may disadvantage parts of the local population, unless offset by fair commercialisation and sharing of generated funds, which CBNRM frameworks often fail to guarantee.⁸³

Another criticism has to do with the balance of power within the community. There is the pervasive issue of *elite capture*, where local elites, whether chiefs, affluent individuals, or those with better education, dominate decision-making and often divert benefits meant for the community to themselves.⁸⁴ A study has revealed a recurring pattern where elites manipulate the devolution of rights to serve their interests, resulting in skewed representation, marginalisation of poorer members, and profit capture at the expense of the wider community.⁸⁵ Elite capture refers to a situation in which resources intended for the broader public good are appropriated by a select few, typically those with significant political or economic clout, ultimately disadvantaging the less influential segments of society.⁸⁶ These few elites are often the ones who participate in decision-making or hold veto power over land-related matters during negotiations with resource-exploiting companies. The degree to which benefits are equitably distributed and the prevalence of elite capture largely depend on the internal power structures within a community, particularly the level of grassroots political awareness and participation, the local land tenure systems, population diversity, and the strength of organised interest groups. Where political engagement is weak and civic participation is minimal, elites find it much easier to dominate and appropriate resources for their own gain.⁸⁷

Research has also revealed that individuals who are wealthier, more educated, and hold higher social status are often disproportionately represented in participatory and democratic systems.⁸⁸ This over-representation allows this privileged minority to monopolise the benefits of natural resources, giving them significant leverage to steer decisions that enhance their own socio-economic standing within the community.⁸⁹

Another criticism of the CBNRM model has to do with its idealized notion of the ‘community’, often portrayed as a unified, harmonious group with shared interests and goals. Critics argue that this assumption is misleading, as it overlooks the internal divisions, conflicts, and diverse interests that frequently exist within local populations.⁹⁰ In reality, communities are rife with inequalities, conflicts, and exploitation, and overlooking internal diversity can undermine the objectives of CBNRM.⁹¹ This over-simplification ignores how power

⁸³ Ibid.

⁸⁴ Saito-Jensen M, Nathan I, Treue T. Beyond elite capture? Community-based natural resources management and power in Mohammed Nagar village, Andhra Pradesh India. *Environmental Conservation*. 2010; 37(3): 327 -33 <doi:10.1017/S0376892910000664> accessed 27 June 2025

⁸⁵ Anna-Lena Mieke, The reality of Community-Based Natural Resource Management in Zambia. *Conservation Insights: Publication of Conservation Biology Group*, November 1, 2024 <<https://www.justiceandconservation.com/post/the-reality-of-community-based-natural-resource-management-in-zambia>> accessed 27 June 2025

⁸⁶ D. Dutta (2009) Elite Capture and Corruption: Concepts and Definitions. In: *National Council of Applied Economic Research*: 1-16.

⁸⁷ Ibid.

⁸⁸ G. Mansuri & V. Rao (2012) Localizing Development: Does Participation Work? *World Bank Policy Research Report*, Washington DC.

⁸⁹ Ibid.

⁹⁰ P. Blaikie (2006) Is small really beautiful? Community-based natural resource management in Malawi and Botswana. In: *World development*, 34(11): 1942-1957.

⁹¹ Washington O. Ochola, Pascal C. Sanginga, Isaac Bekalo (eds.), *Managing Natural Resources for Development in Africa: A Resource Book* (Nairobi: University of Nairobi Press (UONP), 2010) ISBN 9966-792-09-0 (978-9966-792-09-9)

dynamics, social stratification, and intra-community politics shape outcomes, often producing uneven results and even exacerbating local inequities.⁹² According to Cannon, communities often embody the everyday realities of inequality, exploitation, oppression, and even malice, deeply embedded in the dynamics of social relationships.⁹³ The assumptions associated with the use of ‘community’ have been attributed to be responsible for the failure of the CBNRM model in many community-based projects. This oversight stems from a failure to recognise the internal diversity within communities, overlooking how these variations can influence resource management results, shape local political dynamics, and drive strategic interactions. It also neglects the potential for complex, multi-tiered alliances to emerge across various levels of local governance.⁹⁴

9. Host Communities and Rights to Natural Resources

For the purposes of this paper, the terms ‘host communities’, ‘indigenous communities’ and/or ‘resource-bearing communities’ are used interchangeably. That said, this paper shall adopt the definition offered by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) of the phrase ‘*indigenous peoples and local communities*’. According to IPBES, indigenous peoples and local communities (IPLCs) are typically ethnic groups who are descended from, and identify with, the original inhabitants of a given region, in contrast to groups that have settled, occupied, or colonised the area more recently.⁹⁵ International organisations and treaties commonly employ the phrase to describe individuals and groups who identify themselves as indigenous or as part of unique local communities.⁹⁶ Indigenous people usually “maintain an inter-generational historical connection to place and nature through livelihoods, cultural identity, languages, worldviews, institutions, and ecological knowledge”.⁹⁷ Often, these communities maintain a deep, symbiotic relationship with their natural environment, which also makes them particularly vulnerable to the harmful impacts of resource extraction activities carried out in their communities. Acknowledging and upholding the rights of host communities is vital, not only to safeguard their well-being and preserve their cultural heritage, but also to help mitigate unrest and conflicts. Their inclusion in decision-making processes is crucial to ensure their needs and perspectives are genuinely considered. Preserving the cultural heritage and traditional knowledge of indigenous communities also plays a pivotal role in fostering sustainable development. Unfortunately, in Nigeria today, such communities still lack the legal authority to actively participate in the governance and management of the natural resources located within their territories, unlike what is observed in several other parts of the world.

10. Global Consensus on Resource-Bearing Communities’ Rights to Natural Resources

⁹² Ibid.

⁹³ T. Cannon (2008): Reducing people's vulnerability to natural hazards communities and resilience (No. 2008.34). Research paper/UNU-WIDER; See also Environmental Information Service, Namibia (n.15)

⁹⁴ A. Agrawal & C. C. Gibson (1999) Enchantment and Disenchantment: The Role of Community in Natural Resource Conservation. In: *World Development*, 27(4): 629-649.

⁹⁵ See Indigenous Peoples and local communities. *Intergovernmental Science - Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) Secretariat* <<https://www.ipbes.net/glossary-tag/indigenous-peoples-and-local-communities>> accessed 30 June 2025

⁹⁶ Ibid.

⁹⁷ Ibid.

There is a growing global consensus in favour of recognising the rights of resource-bearing communities to the natural resources located within their lands, particularly as a strategy for reducing tensions and restiveness over resource control.⁹⁸ Across the world, many countries have reformed their legal frameworks to grant communities, especially those in resource-rich communities, direct, enforceable rights to these resources. For example, in jurisdiction such as the United States, Alberta (Canada), and South Africa, resource rights are legally recognised to include the sustainable, fair, and equitable management and sharing of benefits, as well as the right to be protected from harmful exploitation of resources.⁹⁹ Specifically, in Alberta, the people legally own the natural resources in their land and are entitled to benefit from their development as a matter of legal right.¹⁰⁰

In contrast, Nigeria is yet to clearly define or effectively implement comparable resource entitlements for host or resource-bearing communities. The rights of these communities to natural resources in their land are yet to be fully crystallised in Nigeria. This pattern is common in many developing nations, where civil and political rights tend to be prioritised over socioeconomic rights that have a direct and daily impact on citizens' livelihoods.¹⁰¹ In Nigeria, the ownership of natural resources is constitutionally vested in the Federal Government.¹⁰² Nevertheless, it may be argued that beyond the ownership regime, resource-based right provisions are enshrined in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. A closer look at the Constitution reveals that the principles underpinning resource rights are embedded in Chapter II thereof, under the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy, which, regrettably, are not justiciable. Notably, Section 17(2)(d) states: "*the exploitation of human or natural resources in any form whatsoever for reasons other than the good of the community shall be prevented.*" This provision implies that the government must always prioritise the interests of communities at the center of resource exploitation efforts and avoid actions that are detrimental to their welfare. Although the provisions in Chapter II lack legal enforceability, they nevertheless impose a moral obligation on the state to manage and distribute natural resources in ways that serve the collective good of all Nigerians, especially those directly impacted by extraction activities.¹⁰³

11. Legal Framework for the Right to Natural Resources in Nigeria

The legal frameworks outlined below are in addition to the sectoral legislations for the extractive industry earlier discussed. The provisions discussed in this segment constitute the broader regulatory provisions that more generally advance the rights of individuals and communities to participate in matters that affect their lives, livelihoods, and overall well-being.

a. African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights

⁹⁸ Yemi Oke (n.1), p.136

⁹⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰⁰ See "Royalties in Alberta", Royalty Review Secretariat, Government of Alberta <http://www.albertaroyaltyreview.ca/more_info/background> accessed 27 June 2025

¹⁰¹ Ibid. 144

¹⁰² See Section 44 (3) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria

¹⁰³ Ibid, section 16 (2) (b)

The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights,¹⁰⁴ a regional legal instrument that has been domesticated in Nigeria, recognises the right of peoples to natural resources. It stands out as one of the most comprehensive rights-based frameworks for the governance of energy and natural resources in the country.¹⁰⁵ Article 21 of the Charter provides:

1. *All peoples shall freely dispose of their wealth and natural resources. This right shall be exercised in the exclusive interest of the people. In no case shall a people be deprived of it.*
2. *In case of spoliation, the dispossessed people shall have the right to the lawful recovery of its property as well as to an adequate compensation.*
3. *The free disposal of wealth and natural resources shall be exercised without prejudice to the obligation of promoting international economic cooperation based on mutual respect, equitable exchange and the principles of international law.*
4. *State Parties to the present Charter shall individually and collectively exercise the right to free disposal of their wealth and natural resources with a view to strengthening African Unity and solidarity.*
5. *State Parties to the present Charter shall undertake to eliminate all forms of foreign economic exploitation particularly that practiced by international monopolies so as to enable their peoples to fully benefit from the advantages derived from their national resources.*¹⁰⁶

In Nigeria, the provisions of the Charter are legally binding, having been ratified and domesticated. By virtue of Section 315 of the 1999 Constitution, the Charter holds the status of an existing law and is regarded as an Act of the National Assembly. This legal proposition was affirmed in the landmark decision of ***Gani Fawehinmi v. Abacha (1996) 9 NWLR (Pt. 475) at 710***, where the Nigerian Court of Appeal recognised the Charter as an enforceable part of Nigerian domestic law. Although its provisions do not supersede the Constitution, they confer enforceable rights and obligations on Nigerian citizens, and the courts are duty-bound to uphold them.¹⁰⁷ That said, despite its legal status, there is currently no known instance in which the Charter's provisions concerning natural resource rights have been judicially tested in Nigeria.

b. The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria

The ownership and control of natural resources in Nigeria are fundamentally a constitutional issue. Section 44(3) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) vests these powers exclusively in the Federal Government. However, as previously discussed in this paper, beyond this centralised ownership framework, resource-related rights are subtly referenced in Chapter II of the Constitution, specifically under the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy. Although these provisions are non-

¹⁰⁴ See African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act, Cap. A9, Vol. 1, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004

¹⁰⁵ Yemi Oke (n.1), p.135

¹⁰⁶ See Section 21 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (n. 96)

¹⁰⁷ Ibid, 147. See also O. Amokaye, 'Human Rights and Environmental Protection: The Necessary Connection' (2007)1:1, Unilag Journal of Human Rights Law, 89 at p.112

justiciable by virtue of Section 6(6)(c),¹⁰⁸ the State nonetheless carries a moral and political obligation to ensure that the country's natural resources are harnessed and distributed to promote the common good.¹⁰⁹ Notably, Section 16(2)(b) of the Constitution mandates that “*the State shall direct its policy towards ensuring that the material resources of the nation are harnessed and distributed as best as possible to serve the common good.*”¹¹⁰

The non-justiciability of Chapter II arises from the fact that its directives are not legally binding unless codified through specific legislation. This position was reinforced by the Supreme Court in *Attorney General of Ondo State v. Attorney General of the Federation*,¹¹¹ where the Court ruled that until the National Assembly enacts laws to operationalize these provisions, they remain unenforceable. An example of such legislative translation is the enactment of the Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Act to give effect to Section 15(5) of the Constitution. Therefore, the implication for natural resource rights under Chapter II is clear: they will remain legally unenforceable until formalised through specific legislation by the National Assembly. Nonetheless, natural resource rights are enforceable under the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, which has been domesticated in Nigeria. Despite its legal standing, the Charter's provisions on resource rights have yet to be tested in Nigerian courts.¹¹²

The enduring inability to enforce Chapter II provisions has fueled longstanding tensions between resource-bearing communities, such as those in the Niger Delta, and the Federal Government on the one hand and resource-exploiting companies on the other.¹¹³ A prominent example is the conflict involving Shell and other oil companies in Ogoniland. The tragic events surrounding the *Shell v. Ogoni episode*,¹¹⁴ which gained international attention and resulted in the loss of prominent Ogoni leaders, highlight the dangers of failing to acknowledge the enforceable rights of resource-bearing communities.¹¹⁵ To assert their rights, the Ogoni people, through the Movement for the Survival of the Ogoni People (MOSOP), developed the famous *Ogoni Bill of Rights* in November 1990, which articulates their demands, including control over the oil resources beneath their land. Similarly, the Ijaw communities issued the *Kaiama Declaration* on December 11, 1998, where representatives from over 500 Ijaw communities declared that all land and resources within Ijaw territory “belong to Ijaw communities.” They also rejected decrees enacted without their consent and demanded the withdrawal of military forces from their region. Moreover, they warned that any oil company

¹⁰⁸ Section 6 (6) (c) provides that: ‘*The judicial powers vested in accordance with the foregoing provisions of this section - shall not except as otherwise provided by this Constitution, extend to any issue or question as to whether any act of omission by any authority or person or as to whether any law or any judicial decision is in conformity with the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy set out in Chapter II of this Constitution*’.

¹⁰⁹ Ibid, section 16 (2) (b)

¹¹⁰ See Section 16(2)(b) of the Constitution

¹¹¹ (2002) 9 NWLR, (Pt. 772) 222.

¹¹² Yemi Oke (n.1), p. 152

¹¹³ Ibid.

¹¹⁴ Yemi Oke (n.1), p. 152, See also A. A. Idowu, “*Environmental Degradation and Human Rights Violation*”, (1999) 3:1 Modern Journal of Finance & Investment Law, 124 at 125 – 128, and Richard Boele, et.al., “*Shell, Nigeria and The Ogoni: A Study of Unsustainable Development*” (No. 1-3) (2001) 9 Sustainable Development, at 74 - 86

¹¹⁵ Yemi Oke (n.1), p. 152

relying on military protection would be seen as a “real enemy.”¹¹⁶ These and other agitations underscore the urgent need to reform the current legal framework of the Nigerian State. A more equitable and environmentally just system must be put in place - one that ensures the participation of resource-bearing communities in the management of resources in the land, and the fair distribution of natural resource benefits through a legally enforceable regime of resource rights.¹¹⁷

12. CONCLUSION

This paper has critically examined the intersection between natural resource governance and the rights of resource-bearing communities in Nigeria. Globally, there is a growing consensus in support of these communities' rights to control and benefit from the natural resources within their territories, as a means of promoting equitable benefit-sharing and reducing unrest linked to resource control struggles. In line with this, many countries have reformed their legal systems to grant direct, enforceable rights to communities in resource-rich areas. In contrast, Nigeria, like many developing countries, continues to vest exclusive ownership and control of natural resources in the Federal Government. While some legal provisions acknowledge host community participation, such recognition remains limited. This centralized model mirrors the hierarchical “top-down” system inherited from colonial rule.

Nevertheless, beyond the ownership framework, resource-based rights are echoed, albeit vaguely in Chapter II of the 1999 Constitution (Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy), though these provisions are non-justiciable. Encouragingly, resource-related rights enshrined in the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, as well as statutory instruments like the Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) and the Minerals and Mining Act, offer a glimmer of hope for communities seeking to assert their rights to participate in the management of the resources in their domains.

The natural resource sector in Nigeria has long been marred by conflicts and militancy, particularly in host communities, underscoring the urgent need for improved governance and conflict resolution strategies. A core driver of this unrest is the inequitable distribution of benefits derived from resources. Given the pivotal role of oil and gas in Nigeria's economy, ensuring uninterrupted extraction is essential. One effective approach is to recognise and uphold the rights of host communities, particularly by promoting inclusive governance and equitable benefit-sharing. Thankfully, statutory frameworks in the extractive sector are beginning to reflect this shift. If properly implemented, these measures could help reduce militancy, sabotage, and attacks on oil installations, trends that have negatively impacted national revenue and the environment, especially in the Niger Delta region of the country. This paper recommends that the Nigerian government further extend the scope of resource-based rights to ensure deeper involvement of resource-bearing communities in resource management. While such involvement may not be a cure-all, it is certainly a meaningful step toward easing tensions or agitation and fostering a more just and sustainable resource governance in Nigeria.

¹¹⁶ See the Ijaw Youths' Kaiama Declaration, 11 December, 1998

waado.org/nigerdelta/RightsDeclaration/KaimaDeclaration.html accessed 27 June 2025

¹¹⁷ Yemi Oke (n.1), p. 153

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